

The Family as the Main Link in Youth Education and Upbringing

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Annotation: This article discusses the importance of the family in youth upbringing, its role in shaping a person's spiritual world, its incomparable place in instilling national values, and raising young people to be well-rounded individuals. It emphasizes the importance of instilling feelings of goodness, patriotism, and love for life in the hearts of young people through family upbringing. It highlights the significance of the family in raising a perfect human being, which is one of the main goals of our national ideology, its role in the upbringing of the nation, and the issues of instilling high intellect, strong faith and upbringing, and national identity in the younger generation, who are the future of our country, through family education.

Keywords: Family, child, childhood, youth, offspring, education-upbringing, family upbringing, mass culture, etiquette, well-rounded generation, future.

The family is the first and most important unit of society, where the first steps of a person's life are taken. It is precisely in the family that a child's worldview, moral standards, and aspirations begin to form. Therefore, the family plays a decisive role in the education and upbringing of young people. "The family is the main unit of society and is under the protection of the state and society."

The role of parents in the comprehensive and spiritual development of a child is immense. Parental love, exemplary lifestyle, and relationships based on mutual respect deeply permeate the child's mind and strongly influence their formation as an individual in the future. Therefore, every family should approach child-rearing with responsibility.

In today's era of globalization, young people are exposed to various information sources. In such circumstances, protecting their minds and hearts from alien ideas and raising them to be loyal to national values, knowledgeable, and patriotic individuals is an important task of the family and society. "Family upbringing plays an important role in raising children and in the comprehensive development of the younger generation by parents, guardians, or older people in the family. In family upbringing, constant educational influence comes from mental tranquility in the family, sincere relationships, high parental authority, maintaining unity among adults in the family when setting demands on children, paying special attention to educating the child for work, loving and respecting the child, establishing a strict regime and daily routine in the family, taking into account the child's age and individual characteristics, monitoring changes in the child, supporting their striving for independence and initiative, and so on. The more orderly the family and sincere the relationships between its members, the more successful the family upbringing will be. In family upbringing, parental authority, their observation, sensitivity, and quick wit are of great educational importance."

The absence of a father or mother, or one of them leaving, causes great harm to family upbringing. Their educational influence on the child disappears, and the balance in family upbringing is disrupted. In such circumstances, the child's heart is severely wounded, they become irritable, quick-tempered, rude, rough, lose trust in adults, and their academic performance declines. The father's authority is of great importance in family upbringing. It is impossible to succeed in raising

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children as well-rounded individuals without connecting the school with the family. Therefore, the joint efforts of the school and parents regarding education and upbringing are of great importance in family upbringing. The opinions expressed during meetings between parents and teachers are especially valuable. Because they learn more about their children. Therefore, every parent who understands the true essence of child upbringing strives to strengthen cooperation between the family and the school.

Until the child finishes school, parents should maintain close contact with the school, be aware of their child's academic progress and behavior, consult with the teacher and class mentor on upbringing matters, and inform the teacher and class mentor about the child's activities after school. In turn, the teacher and class mentor should also provide information to parents about the child's studies, manners, behavior, and conduct at school, and jointly resolve problems that arise when necessary. Parents whose children attend school should become members of the school community. The teacher and class mentor should also establish strong cooperation with their student's family. Cooperation between parents and community activists and labor veterans is also important in family upbringing. Family upbringing can only be successful if favorable conditions are created for the comprehensive development of children. In family upbringing, each family exhibits its unique characteristics.

The feeling of love for the nation and homeland is formed in the minds of our youth in the family and in the neighborhood where they live. The best upbringing is that given by intelligent and perfect parents to their children. In whichever family or neighborhood upbringing is well-established, that family and that neighborhood will prosper.

The question "When should child upbringing begin?" makes many people ponder. According to the encyclopedic scholar Abu Ali Ibn Sina, child upbringing should begin even before birth, from the mother's womb. The family environment becomes stable when parents feel their responsibility. Parental communication plays an important role in child upbringing. If a child grows up hearing harsh and rude words from parents, this negatively affects their nature. This, in turn, leads to the formation of "spiritually ill" individuals from children raised in an unhealthy family environment. These individuals then negatively affect the spirituality of society.

Child upbringing is an extremely complex and responsible process. It requires every parent to constantly work on themselves and stay informed about all matters related to child upbringing. "Although every person is capable of acquiring knowledge from the cradle to the grave, educating a child from childhood is more influential and very important," said Abdurauf Fitrat. Every parent should always keep this thought in mind. Our Prophet (peace be upon him) said in his noble hadith: "Give your children good manners and beautify their manners." Indeed, children adorned with beautiful manners are an important virtue in the sight of the Creator. Understanding this hadith, it is advisable for every parent to pay deep attention to their child's behavior and spirituality and to constantly monitor their upbringing.

Especially in today's era of globalization, the erosion of the true essence of our people's ancient traditions of upbringing, based on unique and appropriate national and religious values, due to the influence of "mass culture" and alien ideas and views on our mentality, causes concern for all of us. If we do not pay serious attention to this process, that is, the issue of upbringing, in a timely manner, it may be too late tomorrow, leading to irreparable consequences. Indeed, we must never forget the words of the famous enlightener Abdulla Avloniy regarding upbringing: "Upbringing for us is a

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matter of either life or death, either salvation or destruction, either happiness or misfortune." Currently, observing the behavior, especially the dress, of some young people makes one ponder. Educating them based on dressing culture and respect for our people's ancient values is an important task.

Today, it has become commonplace for most young people to be busy with their mobile phones in their free time. Modern information and communication technologies, especially the internet, have raised our level of development by several notches, bringing distant things closer and making our work easier. However, there are many aspects that we need to seriously consider regarding young people being enslaved by mobile phones, and their rational use of the internet and social networks, and the information therein. In particular, to prevent our youth from falling under the influence of religious fundamentalism and terrorism ideas spread on the internet, the spread of "mass culture" manifestations, and attempts to make them a part of their lifestyle, and to prevent them from blindly following such deceptions, we must first and foremost enrich their knowledge and thinking, and form the skill of using internet information appropriately and rationally. Unless a spiritual immunity against alien ideas and vices is formed in our youth, we will never be able to escape the threat of information attacks and the vices entering our lives and ideology.

In conclusion, the parent and family environment are of great importance for raising a generation with strong spiritual immunity, who can express their thoughts fluently, and who can achieve high goals. Only a young generation that deeply understands who they are, what invaluable heritage they are heirs to, lives with a sense of love and devotion to their homeland, and has strong faith and conviction, will be able to protect our sacred land from alien and foreign influences and misfortunes, and to comprehensively develop our homeland. Let us raise our children in such a way that they grow up to be loyal to their ancestors, their history, homeland, mother tongue, nation, religion, and traditions.

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